

SYMMETRICAL MULTILEVEL CASCADED H-BRIDGE INVERTER USING MULTICARRIER SINUSOIDAL PULSE WIDTH MODULATION TECHNIQUE

PatilSwapnil Sanjay
Government College of Engineering,
Karad, India
sspatil9552@gmail.com

PatilRupaliTanaji
Government College of Engineering,
Karad, India
rupalipatil269@gmail.com

WategaonkarSuraj Sanjay
Government College of Engineering,
Karad, India
Surajw07@gmail.com

Abstract- This paper investigates and analyses an efficient multicarrier SPWM switching method for cascaded H-Bridge symmetrical multilevel inverter. The H-Bridge based symmetrical multilevel inverter can increase the number of levels of output voltage by adding number of input DC sources. If two DC sources are applied then it gives five levels at output and three DC sources gives seven levels of output. To reduce the THD as per requirement it needs output filter. In this paper multicarrier SPWM switching is provided to the multilevel inverter switches. In this switching method two signals are used, one is reference and another is carrier signal. For SPWM technique reference signal is sinusoidal wave and triangular wave is carrier signal. This type of inverters have an ability to produce waveforms with better harmonic spectrum and realistic output results. The simulation results shows that Total Harmonic Distortion is reduced with sinusoidal pulse width modulation. The simulation results shows that quality of output voltage waveform gets improved with less loss as well as lower THD.

Keywords— Symmetrical Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Inverter, Multicarrier SPWM, Phase Disposed SPWM.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multilevel voltage source inverter structure is very much popular especially in application of conversion of high DC to AC power. Multilevel voltage source is preferred over three level inverter because of its capability of generating the levels of output voltage with less harmonic distortion, lower dv/dt, distortion less input current, reduced common mode voltage and ability to operate at low switching frequency. There are three presentable topologies can be considered for multilevel inverters that is as discussed below:

Diode clamped or neutral clamped, flying capacitors or capacitor clamped and cascaded H-Bridge with separate DC source for each cell. The application of multilevel inverters spreads over the area of static VAR compensation, adjustable power electronic speed drives and conditioning of power line application. Though the multilevel voltage source inverter concept has introduced before three decades, but restricted by its practical application. By using structure of multilevel voltage source inverter, stress on each switching device can be reduced in proportional to number of levels, due to that the inverter can handle higher voltages. By increasing levels of

multilevel inverter, the voltage of output have more stepped like staircase waveform. The cascaded H-bridge multilevel inverter having several switches to increase the levels of output voltage with independent DC voltage sources. This is very simplest structure synthesize a large number of output voltage levels. The characteristics of total harmonic distortion are improved, then it needs to filter the output to meet general requirement of THD. To mitigate this problem, provide efficient multicarrier SPWM technique to switches of multilevel inverter. By providing this SPWM, this operation provides more sinusoidal waveform and less THD. This cascaded H-bridge multilevel inverter is commonly classified as symmetrical CHB as the input DC sources are equal and in series otherwise asymmetrical CHB with different values of DC sources, it will produce more output levels. To verify proposed scheme of cascaded H-bridge multilevel inverter with multicarrier SPWM function implemented in MATLAB simulation.

II. MULTILEVEL SYMMETRICAL CASCADED H-BRIDGE INVERTER

A. Conventional Switching for Symmetrical Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Inverter

Fig1. Five level cascaded H-bridge inverter.

Fig1. Shows five level cascaded H-bridge multilevel inverter. It consists of two cells connected in series and it driven by two different independent voltage sources with same value. i.e. V_1 and V_2 . It synthesizes maximum voltage waveform is the sum of both individual cells output $V_{1+} V_2$. The output voltage of first cell is V_1 and V_2 is for another cell then the output voltage levels become five i.e. $2m+1$; m is the number of input DC voltage sources. The five level outputs are $2V, V, 0, -V, -2V$

TABLE 1

Mode	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈
0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
+V	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1
+2V	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
+V	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1
0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
-V	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
-2V	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0
-V	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1

By providing switching sequence as given in the Table 1 then it will gives stepped output voltage as shown in Fig2. Results will indicate five levels. THD analysis of five level as shown in Fig 3. THD for five level inverter is 26.41%.

Fig2. Five level output voltage as per TABLE1.

Fig3. THD of five level inverter.

If one voltage source is added in five level inverter then it gives output levels seven. If one source is added then four switches are required for that cell and connected in series with another cells. For seven level inverter conventional switching sequence is as given in TABLE 2. If this sequence is employed to particular switches then it will gives seven stepped output as shown in Fig 4. The THD analysis of this output is shown in Fig 5. THD for seven level inverter is 19.16%.

TABLE 2

Mode	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂
0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
V	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
2V	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
3V	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
2V	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
V	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
-V	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
-2V	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0
-3V	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0
-2V	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0
-V	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0

Fig4. Seven level output voltage.

Fig5. THD of seven level inverter.

III. SPWM SWITCHING FOR CASCADED H-BRIDGE MULTILEVEL INVERTER

If we modify the switching of the inverter by multicarrier SPWM technique, it can give more sinusoidal output voltage waveform. The modulation for cascaded H-bridge multilevel inverter is divided into two categories: fundamental switching frequency and high switching frequency PWM, known as multicarrier based PWM, space vector PWM, selective harmonic elimination, and multilevel SPWM. Each independent DC voltage source needs its own carrier.

There are three alternative PWM strategies with differing phase relations:

- APOD (Alternative Phase Opposition Disposition): Every carrier waveform is in or out of phase with its next carrier by 180 degrees.
- POD (Phase Opposition Disposition): Carriers above zero reference are in phase and carriers below zero reference are out of phase with 180 degrees.
- PD (Phase Disposition): All carriers are in phase.

In this proposed cascaded H-bridge multilevel inverter, the phase disposition method is employed to reduce the THD.

Fig6. Multicarrier phase disposition SPWM.

The phase disposition has the following rules:

When the number of levels is five: As the number of voltage levels is five, then the required carriers are $5-1=4$. These four carrier waveforms are arranged such that above and below the zero reference are in phase. Two carriers above and two carriers below the zero reference.

- The multilevel inverter switches ON to +2V when the reference is greater than the second positive carrier wave.
- The multilevel inverter switches ON to +V when the reference is greater than the first positive carrier.
- The multilevel inverter switches to 0 when the reference is less than both positive carriers.
- The inverter switches to -V when the reference is less than the first negative carrier.
- The inverter switches to -2V when the reference is less than the second negative carrier.

When the number of levels is seven: As the number of voltage levels is seven, then the required carriers are $7-1=6$.

By providing switching to the multilevel inverter as discussed above, then it will give results as shown in the simulation results.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The single phase cascaded five-level and seven-level inverter is modeled in MATLAB SIMULINK. The switching for each switch is generated from the different carrier SPWM technique, and THD is analyzed by FFT analysis.

Fig 7. Five level SPWM output voltage.

Total harmonic distortion for this output is as shown in Fig 8. THD for five-level output voltage with SPWM output is 9.09%.

Fig 8. THD for five level SPWM output.

Fig 9. Seven level SPWM output voltage

Total harmonic distortion for this output is as shown in Fig 10. THD for Seven level output voltage with SPWM output is 6.44%.

Fig 10. THD for seven level SPWM output.

CONCLUSION

This paper gives brief idea about implementation of multilevel sinusoidal pulse width modulation (Phase Disposition) for five and seven level inverter. The corresponding FFT analysis has done for single phase. It is

observed that THD for five levels of voltage is 9.09% and for seven levels THD is 6.44%. By using Phase Disposition SPWM strategy it provides lower percentage of THD.

REFERENCES

- [1] Divya Subramanian, Rebiya Rasheed "Five Level Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Inverter Using Multicarrier Pulse Width Modulation Technique" International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology (IJEIT) Volume 3, Issue 1, July 2013
- [2] Julymol Joseph, Arya Prakash "Cascaded Multilevel Inverter With Multicarrier PWM Techniques" [IJESAT] [International Journal of Engineering Science & Advanced Technology] Volume-4
- [3] Won-Kyun Choi, Feel-soon Kang "H-bridge based Multilevel Inverter using PWM Switching Function" 2009 Telecommunications Energy Conference, 2009. 31st International [INTELEC].
- [4] S.M. Ayob, Z. Salam, Member, IEEE and A. Jusoh "Trapezoidal PWM Scheme for Cascaded Multilevel Inverter" 2006 First International Power and Energy Conference PECon 2006 368 November 28-29, 2006.
- [5] Hani Vahedi, Kamal Al-Haddad, Philippe-Alexandre Labbe "Cascaded Multilevel Inverter with Multicarrier PWM Technique and Voltage Balancing Feature" 2014 Industrial Electronics (ISIE), 2014 IEEE 23rd International Symposium on 28 July 2014.
- [6] Abhishek Kumar Ranjan, D. Vijaya Bhaskar, Nibedita Parida "Analysis and Simulation of Cascaded H-Bridge Multi Level Inverter Using Level-Shift PWM Technique" 2015 Circuit, Power and Computing Technologies (ICCPCT), 2015 International Conference on 16 July 2015.
- [7] Rama Ravi Teja, Chiriki Sateesh, Madhuri A. Chowdari "Single Phase 9 Level Symmetrical Cascaded H-Bridge Inverter For Different PWM Techniques" 2017 Electrical Power and Energy Systems (ICEPES), International Conference on 04 May 2017.
- [8] Feel-Soon Kang, Sung-Jun Park, Su Eog Cho "Multilevel PWM Inverters Suitable for the Use of Stand-Alone Photovoltaic Power Systems" IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion (Volume: 20, Issue: 4, Dec. 2005).